

HOMOGENIZATION OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES BASED ON MICRO COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY DATA

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1 Introduction

The field of application of short fiber reinforced composites (SFRC) has been steadily growing in the past years. The main reason for this trend is the increasing effort to build light-weight parts with a higher efficiency or more comfortable use. Due to the relatively ease of manufacturing and the low costs, SFRC, especially with a polymeric matrix, are very attractive for this purpose. The actual reinforcing effect of the fibers depends strongly on the relation between the aspect ratio of the fibers and their orientation. In particular, the orientation of the fibers is influenced by the manufacturing process. Commonly, these composites are manufactured through injection or compression molding.

Even though, SFRC are used for more and more applications, a robust dimensioning of light-weight structures with reinforced materials is still a challenging task. This is due to the fact, that SFRC show heterogeneities on different length scales concerning microstructural properties like fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation distribution. In consequence of the complex material behavior, this class of materials can only partially be modeled by phenomenological approaches. FE² schemes cannot effectively be applied for real microstructures of SFRC since the computational time is prohibitive for appropriate spatial discretizations.

In this paper, different micromechanically based mean field approaches are utilized in order to model a composite material consisting of 30wt.-% of glass fibers reinforcing a polypropylene matrix (PPGF30). The models operate on real microstructure data from micro-computer tomography (μ CT) measurements, which are used to extract the aspect ratio and the orientation of the fibers. The effective linear elastic properties are

determined by different homogenization schemes, and are compared with experimental results out of tensile test.

2 Experimental Setting

2.1 Preparation of Specimen and Tensile Tests

In order to evaluate the elastic properties and the microstructure of PPGF30, thin plates have been manufactured through an injection molding process. The geometry of these plates accounts for the manufacturing process and allows a mainly homogeneous filling of the plate cavity [4]. This geometry and its measures are shown in Fig. 1. The material has been injected via a triangular gating system (A). The specimen for the tensile test and for the μ CT measurement have been prepared from the rectangle section (B).

Fig. 1: Orientation of specimen within an injection molded plate.

Since in case of PPGF30 an anisotropic material behavior can be expected [2, 7, 15, 25], tensile specimens have been prepared with three different orientations out of these plates: in the main flow direction of the material (0°), in the transverse direction (90°) and in a third direction (45°) (see Fig. 1). In terms of pure polypropylene, an isotropic material behavior can be

assumed and thus, only specimen with 0° orientation have been considered. The geometry of the tensile specimen has been chosen according to [22] and is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Geometry of the tensile specimen.

The tensile tests have been performed with the material testing machine Z020 by Zwick-Roell. The deformation has been observed by using 2D digital image correlation [23]. The mean elastic properties of five experiments with PPGF30 specimens and pure PP specimens, respectively, are summarized in Tab. 1. The experimental results for PP serve as isotropic matrix properties in the homogenization procedure described in section 3. In terms of the glass fibers, experiments have not been performed. For the homogenization, isotropic elastic properties of glass have been taken from literature [26] and are also listed in Tab. 1.

Tab. 1: Measured linear elastic properties for PP and PPGF30; elastic constants for glass from [26].

	E [GPa]	ν
Glass	73.0	0.22
PP	1.665	0.364
PPGF30 (0°)	4.482	0.271
PPGF30 (90°)	3.452	0.217
PPGF30 (45°)	3.540	0.304

2.2 Computer Tomography Measurements

It is generally known, that the microstructure significantly affects the mechanical behavior of composites [14, 27]. Besides optical methods [3, 8, 11, 12, 13, 19], μ CT measurements can deliver high-resolution information about the microstructure [6]. Especially for SFRC, the orientation distribution of the fiber axes and the fiber aspect ratios are the dominant characteristics governing the effective material behaviour. They are considered in the following homogenization procedure. In a first step, a μ CT measurement has been performed.

For this purpose, the cylindrically shaped specimen with the diameter $D = 4\text{mm}$ has been extracted from the central position of the injection molded plate in Fig. 1. The measurement itself has been performed on a SkyScan 1072-100 CT apparatus, using its maximum resolution of $1.8\mu\text{m}$. While the specimen is rotating around its vertical axis, it is exposed to x-rays. With each full rotation, the sample is analyzed in small steps on the vertical axis, resulting in a layer wise voxel information of the density distribution. For a detailed description of the μ CT measurement procedure, the reader is referred to literature [5, 6, 10]. In a second step, the 3D voxel data has been analyzed by an in-house tool, which determines the position, the direction, the length, and the diameter of a statistically representative set of the fibers. This data can be used for reconstructions of the microstructure, as shown in Fig. 3. In the following, the reconstructed data is referred as segmented μ CT data.

Fig. 3: Reconstruction of segmented μ CT data for PPGF30.

2.3 Analysis of Microstructure

Usually, the manufacturing of injection molded thin plates, made of SFRC, results in a cross section, the microstructure of which shows three characteristic sections: Near the walls of the plate, the fibers are mainly oriented in flow direction of the material, but in the core section, the orientation of the fibers

is predominantly perpendicular to the flow direction [16, 17, 20, 21]. This observation is also apparent from the reconstruction of the μ CT data in Fig. 3. In order to gain a deeper insight into the properties of the microstructure, the segmented μ CT data has been analyzed in 20 layers. For each layer, the mean length \bar{l}_α and the orientation characteristics in terms of the second-order orientation tensors \mathbf{A}_α defined by

$$\mathbf{A}_\alpha = \sum_{\beta=0}^{N_\alpha} \omega_\beta \mathbf{n}_\beta \otimes \mathbf{n}_\beta \quad (1)$$

have been calculated (see [1]). In the last equation, N_α is the number of fibers in layer α , and ω_β is a weight, which is correlated with the volume fraction of the fiber with the axis direction \mathbf{n}_β . The mean lengths \bar{l}_α , the trace components (A_{11} , A_{22} , A_{33}) and the eigenvalues (λ_1 , λ_2 , λ_3) of \mathbf{A}_α are shown in Fig. 4 to 6 for the segmented μ CT data. From Fig. 4 it is obvious, that the mean length distribution is not constant through the thickness of the plate. In particular, the mean lengths of the layers near the top and bottom wall are slightly higher, than those in the core section. The overall mean length amounts to $330\mu\text{m}$ and is marked in Fig. 4 with a red line.

As expected from experimental observations, the fiber orientation distribution is not constant through the thickness. In Fig. 5, the trace components A_{11} , A_{22} and A_{33} of the second-order orientation tensor \mathbf{A}_α of each layer are shown. Fig. 6 shows eigenvalues of the same orientation tensors \mathbf{A}_α . Both diagrams make clear, that there indeed exists a section in the middle of the specimen with a fiber orientation perpendicular to the major flow direction of the material during the manufacturing process. Especially for the layers 10-12, this fact can be observed. Otherwise, near the top and bottom wall, layers 19-20 and layers 1-2, respectively, the fibers are mainly oriented in the flow direction.

Usually, only the trace components A_{11} , A_{22} and A_{33} of \mathbf{A}_α are shown in literature in order to describe the anisotropy of the orientation of the fibers [18, 28]. Comparing the trace components and the eigenvalues of the orientation tensor \mathbf{A}_α of the 8th and 14th layer reveals, however, that the orientation information is by far not complete if only A_{11} , A_{22} and A_{33} are given.

For both layers, these quantities suggest a planar isotropic distribution of the fibers. Fig. 6 reveals, that for layer 14, indeed a planar isotropic distribution can be found, which is not the case for layer 8.

Fig. 4: Mean length \bar{l}_α (\bullet) of each layer and the whole dataset ($-$).

Fig. 5: Trace components of \mathbf{A}_α : A_{11} (\blacksquare), A_{22} (\bullet), A_{33} (\blacktriangle).

Fig. 6: Eigenvalues of \mathbf{A}_α : λ_1 (\bullet), λ_2 (\blacksquare), λ_3 (\blacktriangle).

The stereographic projections of all fiber axis orientations of layers 8, 11 and 14 in Fig. 7 to 9 confirm the foregoing results. In the pole figures, the out of plane direction corresponds to the filling direction of

the composite during the injection molding process. In the pole figure for layer 8 (Fig. 7), it can be seen, that there exists a preferred orientation of the fibers, which is not captured by the trace components of \mathbf{A}_8 . In contrast to the approximately planar isotropic orientation distribution in layer 14, the pole figure of layer 11 shows an obvious alignment of the fibers in the transverse direction.

Fig. 7: Stereographic projection of fiber axes for layer 8.

Fig. 8: Stereographic projection of fiber axes for layer 11.

Fig. 9: Stereographic projection of fiber axes for layer 14.

The pole figure of the complete segmented μ CT data in Fig. 10 discloses, that the orientation distribution in the whole is only approximately planar isotropic. First, there exist fibers, which are aligned in normal direction

of the plate. Second, within the plane of the plate, a preferred orientation not equal to the flow direction can be noticed. The values for the mean length \bar{l} , the trace components A_{11} , A_{22} , A_{33} and the eigenvalues for the complete dataset are summarized in Tab. 2.

Fig. 10: Stereographic projection of fiber axes of the segmented μ CT data.

Tab. 2: Number of fibers N , mean length \bar{l} , standard deviation of length $\sigma_{\bar{l}}$, trace components and eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} for the segmented μ CT data.

N	6355
$\bar{l}; \sigma_{\bar{l}}$	330.18; 167.4
A_{11}, A_{22}, A_{33}	0.392; 0.584; 0.024
λ_A	0.635; 0.341; 0.024

3 Linear Elastic Properties

To predict the effective elastic properties of the composite described and analyzed in the previous sections, two different micromechanically based mean field approaches have been applied: the self-consistence (SC) homogenization method according to [29], and a two-step bounding method.

3.1 Self-Consistence Homogenization Method

To apply the SC method, the microstructure of a fiber reinforced composite like PPGF30 can be characterized by a distinct matrix and N fibers with the stiffness tensors \mathbb{C}_M and \mathbb{C}_α , respectively. Each fiber, constituted by the fiber axis \mathbf{n}_α and the fiber aspect ratio a_α , is separately used in the SC scheme.

Following [29], the effective elastic stiffness $\bar{\mathbb{C}}$ can be calculated exactly for the given composite by

$$\bar{\mathbb{C}} = \mathbb{C}_M + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N c_\alpha (\mathbb{C}_\alpha - \mathbb{C}_M) \mathbb{A}_\alpha. \quad (2)$$

In the last equation, c_α is the volume fraction of each

fiber, and the fourth-order tensor \mathbb{A}_α is called strain localization tensor. For ellipsoidal inclusions, \mathbb{A}_α is available explicitly. With the approximation of the commonly cylindrical fibers through ellipsoids and the assumption, that each fiber is embedded in an infinite homogeneous matrix consisting of the effective material \mathbb{C}^{SC} , the strain localization tensor \mathbb{A}_α depends on the effective material \mathbb{C}^{SC} , the fiber material \mathbb{C}_α , the orientation of the fiber axis \mathbf{n}_α and the fiber aspect ratio a_α :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{A}_\alpha &= \mathbb{A}(\mathbb{C}^{\text{SC}}, \mathbb{C}_\alpha, \mathbf{n}_\alpha, a_\alpha) \\ &= (\mathbb{I}^s + \mathbb{P}_0^{\text{SC}} (\mathbb{C}_\alpha - \mathbb{C}^{\text{SC}}))^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

\mathbb{P}_0^{SC} is called polarization tensor. This quantity depends on the geometry of the ellipsoidal representation of the fiber and the effective material \mathbb{C}^{SC} (see [29]).

Combining equation (2) and (3), and replacing the exact $\bar{\mathbb{C}}$ with the approximating \mathbb{C}^{SC} gives the implicit conditional equation for the effective linear elastic stiffness:

$$\mathbb{C}^{\text{SC}} = \mathbb{C}_M + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N c_\alpha (\mathbb{C}_\alpha - \mathbb{C}_M) \mathbb{A}_\alpha. \quad (4)$$

This equation is solved numerically using a damped Newton-Raphson method within a Fortran program.

3.2 A Two-Step Bounding Method

Alternatively to the SC homogenization method, two-step bounding methods for the estimation of the effective elastic properties of the composite are applied. In the first step, the matrix material is subdivided and assigned to the fibers. The volume fraction of the matrix attributed to each fiber corresponds to the volume fraction of the fiber c_α with respect to the total fiber volume c_F . Each pair of a fiber and the surrounding matrix material is homogenized by applying the unidirectional (UD) special case of the second-order Hashin-Shtrikman (HS) bounds [24]:

$$\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD}} = \mathbb{C}_M + \frac{c_\alpha}{c_F} (\mathbb{C}_\alpha - \mathbb{C}_M) \mathbb{A}_\alpha. \quad (5)$$

Again, \mathbb{A}_α is the strain localization tensor, but in the context of the bounding method, it does not depend on the effective material like in equation (3) but on a comparison material \mathbb{C}_0 :

$$\mathbb{A}_\alpha = (\mathbb{I}^s + \mathbb{P}^{\text{UD}} (\mathbb{C}_\alpha - \mathbb{C}_0))^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

The polarization tensor \mathbb{P}^{UD} is explicitly known for the UD case [24]. Identifying the comparison material \mathbb{C}_0 with the matrix and the fiber material, gives lower $\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD}-}$ and upper bounds $\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD+}}$, respectively.

As a result of this approach, one obtains the effective bounds $\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD}}$ for the quasi-coated fibers, called domains in the following. The elastic behavior of the domains is transversely isotropic. The homogenization of the elastic behavior of the aggregate of domains is done with two different methods. First, the simple Voigt and Reuss bounds are applied. The corresponding stiffness tensors are denoted by $\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS+V}}$ and $\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS-R}}$, respectively:

$$\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS-R}} = \left(\sum_{\alpha=1}^N \frac{c_\alpha}{c_F} (\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD-}})^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS+V}} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \frac{c_\alpha}{c_F} \mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD+}}. \quad (8)$$

Second, a HS bounding technique is applied assuming isotropic two-point correlation functions [24]. The lower bound for the domains is homogenized with the lower HS bound for the aggregate, whereas the upper bound is homogenized with the upper HS bound. The corresponding stiffness tensors are denoted by $\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS++}}$ and $\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS--}}$, respectively:

$$\mathbb{C}^{\text{HS}\pm} = \left(\sum_{\alpha=1}^N \frac{c_\alpha}{c_F} \mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD}\pm} \mathbb{A}_\alpha^\pm \right) \mathbb{M}^{-1}, \quad (9)$$

with

$$\mathbb{A}_\alpha^\pm = (\mathbb{I}^s + \mathbb{P}_0 (\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD}\pm} - \mathbb{C}_0^\pm))^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbb{M} = \sum_{\beta=1}^N \frac{c_\beta}{c_F} (\mathbb{I}^s + \mathbb{P}_0 (\mathbb{C}_\beta^{\text{UD}\pm} - \mathbb{C}_0^\pm))^{-1}. \quad (11)$$

Now, \mathbb{P}_0 is the polarization tensor for a spherical inclusion, which is embedded in a matrix with the material \mathbb{C}_0^\pm . In case of the upper HS bound, for this material the maximum isotropic part of all $\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD+}}$ is taken. Otherwise, for the lower HS bound of the aggregate, \mathbb{C}_0^\pm is equal to the minimum isotropic part of all $\mathbb{C}_\alpha^{\text{UD-}}$.

4 Results

The isotropic modeling of the constituents of the considered composite has been performed with the four elastic constants from Tab. 1 for PP and glass. Using the segmented μ CT data in combination with the methods described in the previous section, the effective anisotropic stiffnesses have been determined.

In order to compare the elastic properties of the composite for each homogenized elastic stiffness, the direction-dependent Young's modulus has been calculated and evaluated in the corresponding directions (see [9]):

$$\frac{1}{E(\mathbf{d})} = \mathbf{d} \otimes \mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbb{S}[\mathbf{d} \otimes \mathbf{d}]. \quad (12)$$

In the last equation, \mathbf{d} is the direction vector, which has been parameterized with spherical coordinates $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{d}(\vartheta, \varphi)$. The graphical representation of this quantity is called isospherical projection of the Young's modulus. In Fig. 11, the isospherical projection of the Young's modulus for the effective stiffness of the SC method is shown exemplarily. In this diagram, the value of the Young's modulus is indicated by the length of a vector from the origin to a certain point on the displayed surface. Therefore, the negative values on the coordinate axes in Fig. 11 and in similar figures do not result in negative Young's moduli.

Fig. 11: Graphical representation of direction dependent Young's modulus.

For the results shown in Fig. 12, the direction dependent Young's modulus has been evaluated in the main flow direction of the material during the manufacturing process (E_1), the transversal direction (E_2), and the 45° direction (E_3). Due to the anisotropic distribution of fibers, the Young's modulus in the $+45^\circ$ or -45° direction is not equal in the latter case. Since experimental measurements are only available in one direction, the mean of both values is used for E_3 with the intent to compare the experimental result.

Fig. 12: Young's modulus in 0° (E_1), 90° (E_2) and 45° direction (E_3) for the segmented μ CT-data for SC (\bullet), HS-R/HS+V ($\blacklozenge, \blacksquare$), HS-/HS++ ($\blacktriangle, \blacktriangledown$), Exp. (\times)

In this diagram, the experimental values are marked through a red cross and are located between the bounding values. The SC results are also located between the bounding values. In all directions, the difference between the two lower or upper bounds of the different two-step approaches $E^{\text{HS-R}}$ ($E^{\text{HS+V}}$) and $E^{\text{HS--}}$ ($E^{\text{HS++}}$) is small. The Young's modulus values for the two-step method, whereby in each step the HS approach is used, $E^{\text{HS--}}$ and $E^{\text{HS++}}$ are slightly closer to each other than $E^{\text{HS-R}}$ and $E^{\text{HS+V}}$. The difference is, however, not significant. The SC method predicts in all cases a greater Young's modulus compared to experimental results.

In Fig. 13, the deviation, defined by

$$\Omega = \frac{|E^{\text{hom}} - E^{\text{exp}}|}{E^{\text{exp}}}, \quad (13)$$

of SC results to the experimental measurements is shown. Depending on the orientation, the deviation ranges between 8% in 0° direction and 17% in 45° direction.

In order to reveal the effect of the homogenization procedure on the anisotropy of the predicted material behavior, the ratios E_2/E_1 , E_3/E_1 and E_2/E_3 have been calculated for experimental and homogenized values of $E(\mathbf{d})$. In Fig. 14, the ratios of the numerical data are compared to the ratios of experimental data. Thus, an exact match of the simulated anisotropy ratio would lie on the diagonal in this diagram. Ratios lying above the diagonal line, indicate an under-estimation of the anisotropy. Otherwise, ratios below the diagonal line indicate an overestimation of the considered anisotropy, and ratios equal to one stand for vanishing anisotropy.

Fig. 13: Deviation of numerical results vs. experiments of the Young’s modulus in flow (E_1), transversal (E_2) and 45° direction (E_3)

All homogenization methods predict a smaller anisotropy for E_2/E_1 and E_3/E_1 . A higher anisotropy is predicted for E_2/E_3 . Especially for E_2/E_1 and E_3/E_1 , the SC method matches the anisotropy better than the two-step approaches. However, the results of the two-step methods for E_2/E_3 show a better prediction of the experimental data than those of SC. It is interesting to notice, that the ratios of the lower bounds of the two step methods are closer to experimental ratios than those of the upper bounds, whereas the latter are on an similar elevated level in all directions, being an indicator for a close to isotropic symmetry.

Fig. 14: Anisotropy of Young’s Modulus for the segmented μ CT data: $E_\alpha^{SC}/E_\beta^{SC}$ (●), $E_\alpha^{HS-R}/E_\beta^{HS-R}$ and $E_\alpha^{HS+V}/E_\beta^{HS+V}$ (■), $E_\alpha^{HS--}/E_\beta^{HS--}$ and $E_\alpha^{HS++}/E_\beta^{HS++}$ (▲), experimental ratios (○).

In a more qualitative manner, the anisotropy of the

resultant Young’s modulus can be analyzed through observations of the shape of its isospherical projection. Fig. 15 to 17 present the directional-dependent Young’s modulus in the x - z -, y - z - and x - y -plane. Since the tensile tests have been performed with specimens prepared in the x - y -plane, the available experimental data can be added to the isospherical projection of the Young’s modulus shape curves in Fig. 17. In this plane, as well, it is visible, that there is no distinct value for the Young’s modulus in $\pm 45^\circ$ -direction. All plane representations reveal the circumstance, that the upper bounds of the two step approaches do not reproduce the anisotropy of the microstructure accurately. They predict a more isotropic material behavior.

Fig. 15: Orientation dependence of Young’s modulus in the x - z -plane: SC (∖), HS-Voigt/Reuss (∖), HS-HS (∖).

Fig. 16: Orientation dependence of Young’s modulus in the y - z -plane: SC (∖), HS-Voigt/Reuss (∖), HS-HS (∖).

Fig. 17: Orientation dependence of Young's modulus in the x - y - plane: SC (∇), HS-Voigt/Reuss (\backslash), HS-HS (\sphericalangle), experiments (\circ).

5 Summary and Concluding Remarks

In this paper, a composite composed of polypropylene reinforced with 30wt.-% of short glass fibers has been examined. The experimental procedures consisting of tensile tests in three different directions and μ CT measurements of cylindrical specimen have been combined with a stochastic fiber analysis method. The resulting segmented μ CT data, which describe a representative amount of fibers in the specimen via the parameters length, radius, and orientation, has been used within two different mean field homogenization approaches in order to predict the elastic properties. Therefore, the approximating self-consistence method and a two-step bounding method have been applied.

Based on the experimental results and their comparison to the numerical calculations, following conclusions can be made:

- The mechanical behavior of a PPGF30 under quasistatic tension loading was thoroughly investigated by means of 2D digital image correlation.
- The anisotropic nature of SFRC, which was evaluated by conducting experiments in different material orientations, shows the great importance of gaining detailed knowledge of the fiber configuration for the dimensioning of the composite.
- The segmented μ CT data allows for an accurate observation of the microstructure of short fiber reinforced composites. This includes the

analysis of the specimen in a layer-wise manner, thereby delivering the variation of the fiber orientation and fiber aspect ratio depending on the position in the specimen.

- The discussed mean field homogenization approaches are capable of handling the segmented μ CT data and taking into account the anisotropic distribution of the fiber axes, the length, and the radius distribution. Operating on this discretized data, the considered methods deliver anisotropic elastic stiffnesses. The anisotropy is caused by the microstructure properties.
- The two-step approach has been applied in two variants: In the first step of both variants, the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds for unidirectional aligned fiber domains are applied, while in the second step, a simple averaging of the stiffnesses or again a Hashin-Shtrikman procedure for polycrystal-like structures has been used. Nevertheless, a comparison of the resulting Young's modulus has revealed, that the difference between these two methods is not significant.
- In the discussed cases, the self-consistence homogenization method based on the segmented μ CT data predicts a stiffer material behavior compared to experiments. Compared with the two-step approach, the self-consistence method gives the most accurate approximation of the anisotropy of the experimentally measured Young's modulus.

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